

Asp. Net Framework in Model View Controller Implementation

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Abstract— The Model-View-Controller (MVC) architectural pattern divides an application into three logical components: model, view, and controller. Each of these components is designed to handle unique aspects of application creation. MVC is a common industry-standard web development platform for developing scalable and extensible projects. This pattern has become common for developing web applications and mobile applications after being traditionally used for desktop graphical user interfaces (GUIs). Popular programming languages such as Javascript, Python, Perl, C#, Java, Swift, and Elixir have MVC frameworks that can be used to quickly build mobile or web applications.

Keywords —model, view, controller, web development, mobile application development, MVC framework.

I. INTRODUCTION

The idea of using MVC pattern is to build a web application or mobile application in a more efficient way than other ways like web forms. MVC pattern will make us the job easier for developing a web application in many possible ways. As we all know MVC stands for Model View Controller. Model is the central component of the MVC pattern, it is the applications dynamic data structure and it is independent of the user interface. It is the data structure itself and manages rules and logic for the application. The second part of the MVC is the View which specifies the user interface that is the view for our application, whatever we see in the application output is the View part of the MVC pattern. And the final part is the Controller which is the main part for the application being developed, the controller accepts input from the model or view and converts it to commands which is being executed in our project, it can be referred to as backbone of our project where the main part that is the code is being executed. The controller respond the users input and validates it with the model and give the output to the user. The World Wide Web is increasingly expanding, and an increasing number of governmental and nongovernmental organizations, private businesses, universities, and research institutes are using it to present their material. It's difficult to tell the difference between user interface and business logic. The Model-View-Controller (MVC) pattern divides an application into three parts: the Model, View, and Controller. This is extremely difficult to do with static HTML pages. We need several strategies to conveniently distinguish the user interface logic from the business logic. Connect the user interface to the

Web and present the contents dynamically. Dynamically present the contents on the site. There are several methods for connecting a user interface to the Internet, but each method has its own set of benefits and drawbacks. Choosing the best solution for a specific problem in a specific context is extremely difficult. We define and investigate Active Server Pages (ASP) in this paper, which are the most critical techniques for implementing MVC in the ASP.Net environment. This seems to be a natural solution, but it has some major flaws. One issue is that the user interface is much more likely to alter than the data storage structure. Another issue with tying the data and user interface parts together is that business applications often have business logic that extends beyond data transmission

Model: The model is in charge of the application domain's behavior and data, as well as responding to requests for information about its state (typically from the view) and commands to modify state (usually from the controller).

View: The view is in charge of how information is shown..

Controller: The controller interprets the user's mouse and keyboard inputs, causing the model and/or view to alter accordingly.

Figure 1: MVC class structure

ASP.Net and Model View Controller is shown in Figure 6. The most important of all of the objects above, are the business objects that are the controller objects.

Figure 6: The class diagram for logon Screen

IV. ASP.NET APPLICATION

A web application with a master page that includes a corporate logo, banner, main content, and footer is used to show the ASP.Net framework. A parent-child connection should be visible in the main contents of a grid view. On top will be the main grid, and on the bottom will be the information grid. The details/child view should shift when the user clicks on any object in the master view, and should display the relevant child data as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: The view/manipulate of the master-details (prototype)

The master page design is shown in Figure 8. So,

Figure 8: The master page design

We get exactly what we see. A MasterPage, an HTML frame container, and an HTML table would make up our application. The HTML table would also include the Master-User-Control and Details-User-Control controls. The MasterDataGrid and other user controls would be contained within these user controls.

DetailsDataGrid views. Figure 9 shows the necessary static inventory of the objects, needed to fulfill this job.

- Master page
 - > HTML Frame
 - > HTML Table
 - >MasterUserControl
 - >MasterDataGrid
 - >DetailsUserControl
 - >DetailsDataGrid

Figure 9. The static inventory of the objects

V. ROBUSTNESS ANALYSIS OF THE ASP.NET APPLICATION.

We now have a basic understanding of the artefacts required to complete this task, but before moving on to the detailed design, we must first examine the application using UML to determine the appropriate interactions and relationships between them. This can be accomplished by doing a robustness analysis while holding the MVC principle in mind. Figure 10 depicts the conceptual robustness diagram for this case. Figure 10 also illustrates how a master-details view is shown to the consumer. The master table objects are selected using the upper Master-Grid-view. As a result, if the user chooses master

Figure 10: The Robustness Analysis Diagram for Master Detail Tables Relationships

item, the child view is updated accordingly. When the user selects an item from the master-grid-view, the MasterUserController object is notified, and the listener, which is the MainController object, is notified. The other listener and the DetailsUserController will be notified of this event by the MainController object. These user-controls can be accessed

directly to the model (DataAccessGateway) that uses MsSqlDataLinkAdapter to establish MS-SQL database connections. Figure 11 shows the objects interaction diagram for this scenario.

Figure 11: The objects interaction diagram for this scenario

Differential controllers are the MasterController and the DetailsController. This means they're in charge of fine-tuning and manipulating one user-control at a time, while the MainController object serves as an integrator. The INotifier interface must be implemented by a notifying object, while the IListner interface must be implemented by a listener object. In order to be alerted, a listener object must also be attached to the appropriate notifier. We have the Master-Controller in our situation, and the Details-Controller is the listener. MainController serves as a connector between listeners and notifiers. However, we now have all of the knowledge we need about the artefacts in charge of doing the job, as well as their actions and functionality. Figure 12 depicts the MasterPage class in its entirety.

Figure 12: The complete class design for Master-Page

THE MAIN ADVANTAGES OF ASP.NET MVC

1. Gives you complete control over the rendered HTML.
2. Provides a clear line of demarcation between problems (SoC).
3. Enables Test Driven Development (TDD).
4. Easy integration with JavaScript frameworks.
5. Following the design of stateless nature of the web.
6. RESTful urls that enables SEO.
7. No ViewState andPostBack events

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VI. CONCLUSIONS

The MVC pattern is supported by the ASP.NET framework. The MVC pattern is supported by the Page Controller pattern in the ASP.NET system. Each tab, however, has a code-behind that acts as the controller. Since there is no centralized controller, MVC can be easily implemented in ASP.NET.

VII. FUTURE WORK

Web applications are exploding in popularity in today's world. Web technologies are now used in a variety of areas, including e-commerce, finance, medical, sports, entertainment, and education. The patience of web application users is dwindling as web application growth progresses. Any page of a web application that takes too long to load can irritate the user. The user actually turns to another alternative because he or she has more choices. As a result, the emphasis of this paper is on how to make a web application react quickly in order to maintain a growing number of users. We used two separate technologies to compare the performance of a web application built on the MVC architecture. As a result, we can infer that a website built on the MVC architecture performs better than one built on the .net system.

VIII. REFERENCES

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